

Optimization of Equilibrium Core Shuffling Scheme for Extended Power Uprate Scenarios

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ABSTRACT

Power uprating of existing light water reactors provides a practical and economical means of expanding U.S. nuclear generation capacity without new construction. Extended power uprates, which increase thermal power beyond 7%, require redesign at both the core and plant levels to ensure safety and performance compliance. This investigation advances current uprate analysis by integrating low-enriched uranium+ fuel, enriched up to 7.95 wt% ²³⁵U, with burnable absorbers into an optimized equilibrium core shuffling scheme for the South Texas Project Unit 1 pressurized water reactor. Using a POLARIS/PARCS modeling sequence, multiparameterized cross sections were generated and applied in full-core simulations. Core optimization was performed using the MIDAS optimization framework with a genetic algorithm to satisfy safety and performance constraints under uprated conditions. An initial 18% uprate and cycle extension of 6 months demonstrated the feasibility of uprated operation but revealed persistent violations of rod enthalpy rise hot channel factor and rod burnup limits due to local power peaking. Incorporating uranium-gadolinia fuel designs improved reactivity control but did not fully resolve the peaking behavior. Two performance reducing scenarios, a high power uprate and a low power uprate, achieved near-compliance with all objectives, demonstrating a more practical near-term operation objective. The results establish that uprate feasibility in existing pressurized water reactors is constrained by intra-assembly power peaking as it translates and amplifies in core power peaking limits. Future work is to incorporate hybrid burnable absorber configurations with integrated fuel burnable absorber and gadolinia to enable low-enriched uranium+ based uprates within regulatory safety margins.

Keywords: Power Uprate, Core Optimization, Burnable Absorbers, Low-Enriched Uranium+, Pressurized Water Reactor

1. INTRODUCTION

Power uprating of existing light water reactors (LWRs) has emerged as a practical approach to expand U.S. nuclear generating capacity using the current reactor fleet [1]. Extended Power Uprates (EPU), increases in thermal power beyond 7%, require both core-level and plant-level redesign, often including new fuel concepts, modified reload strategies, and updated safety analyses [2]. Recent advancements in Low-Enriched Uranium+ (LEU+) fuels (enrichments up to 10 wt% ²³⁵U) and Accident Tolerant Fuel (ATF) systems provide pathways to support EPU by extending cycle length, improving thermal margins, and enabling higher energy extraction. These developments must be coupled with optimized fuel loading and burnable absorber distribution to balance reactivity and power peaking while maintaining performance objectives. This study evaluates the technical feasibility of a substantial power uprate in a pressurized water reactor (PWR) using LEU+ fuel at high burnup, emphasizing core design optimization under uprated conditions. The South Texas Project (STP) Unit 1 was selected as a representative U.S. PWR for analysis. Core simulations were performed using the 3-D nodal code PARCS [3], and the POLARIS code [4] for multi-parameterized cross-section generation of fuel assembly loading configurations. The uprated core was subsequently optimized to meet reactivity, thermal-hydraulic, and burnup constraints.

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2. STP CORE MODEL

The EPU scenarios analyzed in this work was applied to the STP Unit 1 PWR reactor design [5]. The core consists of 14-ft (4.27 m) fuel assemblies within a 304 stainless steel reactor vessel cooled by borated water. Axial neutron reflectors, 10 in. (25.4 cm) tall, are positioned above and below the active core. Each assembly uses a 17×17 pin array, including 264 fuel rods, one central instrumentation tube, and 24 guide tubes for control rods. The fuel assemblies use UO₂ enriched to 4.2% or 4.6% ²³⁵U by weight, with reactivity controlled by integral fuel burnable absorber (IFBA) rods. Assemblies with 4.2% ²³⁵U contain 64, 105, or 128 IFBA rods, while those with 4.6% ²³⁵U contain 128, resulting in four total fuel assembly loading designs. IFBA rods use UO₂ pellets with ZrB₂ coating, where boron acts as a burnable absorber. All four assembly designs share the same axial layout with a total height of 168 in (426.7 cm). The top and bottom 8 in (~ 20 cm) form blanket regions with 2.6% ²³⁵U enrichment and no IFBA coating.

An equilibrium cycle shuffling scheme was developed for STP Unit 1 as a pre-uprated reference. The equilibrium cycle represents a steady-state operating condition in which fuel loading, burnup, and reactivity distributions are identical between cycles, making it a consistent baseline for evaluating extended power uprate feasibility.

3. OPTIMIZATION METHODOLOGY

The design space for the STP model equilibrium shuffling scheme is extremely large, with 193 fuel assembly positions and a substantial fuel inventory consisting of both fresh and burned fuel for various fuel assembly loading designs. To find equilibrium shuffling schemes (core designs) that meet the desired objectives, an equilibrium core optimization problem was implemented in the MIDAS optimization framework [6], using a genetic algorithm with tuned hyperparameters to effectively explore and exploit the solution space. The objective function of a solution was formulated as a penalty-based fitness function

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Fitness} = & -W_{RBU} \cdot \max\left(0, RBU_{\text{limit}} - RBU\right) - W_{F_q} \cdot \max\left(0, F_{q,\text{limit}} - F_q\right) \\ & - W_{F_{\Delta H}} \cdot \max\left(0, F_{\Delta H,\text{limit}} - F_{\Delta H}\right) - W_{\text{Boron}} \cdot \max\left(0, \text{Boron}_{\text{limit}} - \text{Boron}\right) \\ & - W_{EFPD} \cdot \max\left(0, EFPD_{\text{limit}} - EFPD\right) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where violations of constraints reduced fitness and compliant solutions received no penalty. Constraints included key safety and performance parameters, such as the enthalpy rise hot channel factor ($F_{\Delta H}$), the heat flux hot channel factor (F_q), maximum soluble boron concentration, maximum rod burnup (RBU), and cycle length, measured in Effective Full Power Days (EFPD). Each constraint was initially weighted so that violations produced comparable penalties; these weights were then strategically adjusted in subsequent optimization runs to reflect evolving parameter priorities. Safety metrics were derived from the current plant design, while performance metrics reflected EPU objectives.

To obtain a more accurate estimate of maximum RBU, rod-based power factors were applied. PARCS reconstructs rod powers from the nodal power and lattice pin power map. Similarly in this work, the RBU is estimated considering the nodal burnups and lattice pin powers

$$BU_{\text{rod},i} = BU_{\text{rod},i-1} + \frac{P_{\text{rod},i} \cdot G_{\text{assembly}}}{P_{\text{assembly}} \cdot G_{\text{rod},i}} \left[BU_{\text{assembly},i} - BU_{\text{assembly},i-1} \right] \quad (2)$$

where the reconstructed rod power, P_{rod} is divided by the assembly power, P_{assembly} to obtain a local power factor, which is then scaled by the ratio of heavy metal loading G in the rod to that of the assembly. This coefficient is multiplied by the change in burnup, BU between depletion steps, i , and

accumulated over the cycle, assuming an initial uniform burnup distribution within each assembly for simplification.

4. EPU CORE DESIGN APPROACHES

To develop a core that meets the required safety limits and performance objectives, an iterative workflow was carried out between fuel assembly design and overall core design. Throughout this process, different enrichment levels and burnable absorber configurations were evaluated and refined. The evolution of both the fuel assembly and core design is summarized in the subsections that follow.

4.1. EPU Core Design with IFBA-LEU+ Fuel Assemblies

The initial stage of optimization evaluated the feasibility of achieving a large power uprate in the existing STP reactor configuration, named EPU 1. Specifically, the optimization targeted an EPU exceeding 18%, increasing thermal power from 3,800 MW to 4,500 MW and extending the cycle length from 18 months (530 EFPD) to 24 months (700 EFPD), with associated thermal-hydraulic changes implemented to enable this uprate. The EPU 1 performance objectives increase the energy extracted per cycle, where the previous fuel assembly designs were unable to achieve the required heavy metal loading. Consequently, new assemblies were proposed using LEU+ fuel enriched between 5–10 wt% ²³⁵U, specifically at 7.50%, 7.75%, and 7.95%.

Higher enrichment introduces challenges such as increased neutron activity and reactivity. While reactivity can be mitigated through greater use of burnable absorbers and soluble boron, the initial excess reactivity from LEU+ fuel remains substantial. To best handle the excess reactivity, all fuel assemblies within the core were loaded with 128 IFBA rods. Optimization of the equilibrium cycle in MIDAS after the uprate achieved all design goals, including 4,500 MWth output and a 700 EFPD cycle length, as summarized in Table I.

Table I. Summary of key performance parameters and safety limits of EPU 1 Core.

Objective	Value	Limit
Max. Cycle Length (EFPD)	718	700
Max. Soluble Boron (ppm)	2678	1800
EOC Peak Exposure (GWd/MTU)	97.05	—
P _{xyz}	1.944	2.100
P _{xy}	1.492	1.650

As expected, enrichment increases necessitated higher soluble boron levels, though minimized within the optimization. The extended operation resulted in a high end-of-cycle (EOC) peak fuel assembly exposure of 97.05 GWd/MTU relative to NRC limits [7], but the objective was not included in the initial optimization as meeting the design goals was the primary objective. At the assembly level, the power peaking factors were able to meet their specified limits. To more accurately assess a design’s compliance with safety limits, rod-based peaking factors were implemented in MIDAS for subsequent optimization cases. The results indicate that 128 IFBA rods per assembly were insufficient to mitigate the excess reactivity introduced by LEU+ fuel enrichments; therefore, a more effective burnable absorber was incorporated into the fuel assembly design.

4.2. Fuel Assembly Design with Gadolinia-LEU+

To achieve more effective reactivity control, gadolinia (Gd₂O₃) was introduced into the fuel matrix, forming urania-gadolinia fuel pellets. Fuel designs with enrichments of 7.5%, 7.75%, and 7.95% were

evaluated, each with varying gadolinia loadings from 2-8 wt% Gd_2O_3 , and loading configurations M1, M2, M3, M4, M8, and M9 [6, 8]. As seen in Figure 1, the gadolinia loaded fuel rods (blue) are effective in suppressing the power distribution in the fuel assembly due to their high absorption cross sections and weight percentage.

Figure 1. Radial power factor (RPF) distribution of the M8 fuel assembly loading configuration with 7.00% enrichment.

Initial screening assessed each design's ability to maintain criticality throughout the equilibrium cycle using a 0-D linear reactivity core model, assuming flat power distributions, equal batch sizes, and a single assembly type. This 0-D model is based on the relationships and assumptions described in the linear reactivity model [9]. Using the 0-D approach, key parameters such as cycle criticality can be estimated efficiently, without using computationally intensive simulations, allowing for quick and informed selection of promising fuel assembly loading designs. Regional burnups were mapped to each fuel assembly's infinite multiplication factor (k_{∞}), or reactivity, curve to interpolate EOC values, as summarized in Figure 2. A 94% non-leakage (NL) probability was applied for the predicted core reactivity, where designs not satisfying this condition were deemed unable to sustain full cycle criticality.

Assuming a linear relationship between the combined k_{∞} of two assemblies, pairing a "high-reactivity" and "low-reactivity" design was expected to achieve adequate EOC reactivity. These pairings were retained for further analysis, while combinations where both designs were above or below the leakage threshold were excluded. A linear programming (LPR) model was used to refine the viable pairings by identifying configurations that satisfied physical constraints and target cycle length. The LPR optimization determined that the minimum feed region size satisfying criticality constraints was 84 assemblies. The primary objective minimized EOC criticality deviation while considering gadolinia loading for improved BOC reactivity control. Based on LP results, the selected combination, 7.95%-M8 and 7.75%-M1, achieved sufficient EOC reactivity for the desired cycle length and has one of the highest gadolinia loadings among all evaluated pairings.

4.3. EPU Core Design with Gadolinia-LEU+ Fuel Assemblies

In successive optimization cases informed by the 0-D model, where 16,800 core designs were evaluated for each case, none of the evaluated core designs were able to meet the maximum RBU limit for EPU

Figure 2. EOC criticality for fuel assembly loading configurations at various enrichments based on 0-D model.

1 objectives. The consistent overutilization of fuel, resulting in elevated peak RBU values, suggests that the EPU 1 objectives are overly ambitious, leaving few, if any, viable designs within the solution space that satisfy the maximum RBU limit. Consequently, the next step was to either modify system parameters, such as fuel enrichment, or revise the performance objectives to achieve feasible operation. To address the excessive maximum RBU observed in the EPU 1 scenario, the performance goals were refined to produce two more practical uprate scenarios, with one maintaining the higher power level but reducing cycle length (High Power Uprate, HPU) and one maintaining the longer cycle but reducing the uprate magnitude (Low Power Uprate, LPU), as described in Table II.

Table II. Comparison of nominal and uprated operating parameters.

Parameter	Nominal Value	EPU 1	LPU	HPU
Power Uprate (%)	0.00	18.42	8.00	18.42
Power Rating (MWth)	3,800	4,500	4,100	4,500
Cycle Length (EFPD)	530	700	700	530
Feed Region Sizes	72	84	88	84, 68
Cycle Burnup (GWd/MTU)	15.41	24.10	21.96	18.25

As the new scenarios resulted in a reduction in cycle burnup, estimated by the linear reactivity model, adjustments were made to the fuel assembly enrichments, fuel inventory, and the feed region size.

The reduction in the cycle burnup requirement in the HPU case allowed for a reduced feed region size of 68 assemblies using the same fuel assembly loading designs, based on the 0-D model; however, a feed region size of 84 was maintained for a case as well. In the reduced feed region size case, fewer than half of the designs met the cycle length limit, while most 84-assembly designs satisfied it but exceeded the target cycle length.

The LPU scenario, with slight reduction in cycle burnup compared to the EPU 1, explored whether lower enrichments could meet the extended cycle length. The same 0-D model was used assuming a linear decline in EOC k_{∞} with decreasing enrichment. The M8, which uses 44 gadolinia loaded fuel rods, resulted in a lower range of possible enrichments to maintain criticality, but with high gadolinia

loading to handle BOC reactivity, relative to the other designs. To reduce the size of the design space, only the M8 design was used in the core design. Fuel assembly designs were evaluated at 7.0% and 7.25% enrichments, with gadolinia concentrations adjusted accordingly. The optimization maintained the same objective-function framework but increased weighting on the $F_{\Delta H}$ constraint while expanding the feed region to up to 88 assemblies to aid in reducing maximum RBU as the objective function was shifted to prioritize $F_{\Delta H}$.

The results between all optimization cases showed to find a design that met all of the constraints except for $F_{\Delta H}$ for a given scenario, thus optimal designs were selected based on the number of constraints met and closeness to meeting the $F_{\Delta H}$ limit (Table III).

Table III. Summary of results for optimal HPU and LPU core designs with their respective limits.

Objective	HPU Value	HPU Limit	LPU Value	LPU Limit
Max. Cycle Length (EFPD)	537	530	730	700
Max. Soluble Boron (ppm)	1488	1800	1461	1800
Max. Rod Burnup (GWd/MTU)	79.66	80.00	78.58	80.00
F_q	2.399	2.550	2.527	2.550
$F_{\Delta H}$	1.795	1.620	1.873	1.650

As no restrictions were applied to the composition or batch origin of discharged fuel assemblies, the shuffling schemes varied, allowing fuel assemblies of either design to be discharged from any batch. The best-performing HPU configuration met the maximum RBU constraint, but exceeded the $F_{\Delta H}$ limit by 9.0%. The single fuel assembly loading design cores with reduced enrichment levels (7.0% and 7.25%) were able to meet the performance objectives. Maximum RBU distributions for both enrichments centered around 96 GWd/MTU ± 5 , with only one design meeting the RBU limit in the 7.0% case. The best-performing LPU design, which was limited to one design based on the number of constraints met criterion, exceeded the $F_{\Delta H}$ limit by 11.9%.

As both designs failed to meet the $F_{\Delta H}$ limit, a closer examination of where and when the exceedance occurs was conducted. For both designs, the limit violation occurs at or near the BOC of the cycle and in fresh fuel assemblies. The peaking radial power factor (RPF) fuel rod for the HPU best core design occurred in the top-left quadrant of the fuel assembly near the corner guide tubes, in which the quadrant is the closest to the center of the core. The peaking RPF fuel assembly for the LPU best core design occurred in fuel assembly G-4 (Figure 3). As the fuel assembly's bottom-right corner was the closest to the core center, the peak RPF fuel rod was located in the bottom-right corner, at the 17-17 location of the fuel assembly (Figure 3).

5. RESULTS DISCUSSION

The decision to reduce the EPU 1 performance objectives enabled more designs to meet the maximum RBU limit, particularly under the HPU scenario. Since the fuel assembly loading designs were identical between the EPU 1 and HPU cases, this outcome suggests that the average enrichment of fuel assemblies in the feed region, relative to the estimated cycle burnup, serves as an indicator of whether core designs can meet the burnup limit. Furthermore, the success of the core designs in meeting the performance objectives under the LPU and HPU scenarios highlights the effectiveness and computational efficiency of the 0-D model in guiding the selection of fuel assembly loading designs.

Because there were no constraints on the composition of discharged fuel assemblies, low-reactivity assemblies were often discharged from the most burned regions. This led to potential overutilization and excessive energy extraction from these assemblies and their corresponding fuel rods. Imposing tighter constraints on the discharge batch composition, specifically based on the reactivity level of the

Figure 3. Close examination of the core RPF distribution and the location of the peaking RPF fuel rod.

fuel assembly loading design, could improve compliance with the maximum RBU limit.

The most persistent issue across all scenarios and optimization cases was the inability to identify a design that met the $F_{\Delta H}$ constraint. The repeated $F_{\Delta H}$ exceedance was traced to rod power peaking inherent to the evaluated fuel assembly designs. A comparison between the M8 fuel assembly RPF distributions and the peaking RPF fuel assemblies from the LPU core design simulation demonstrated that the intra-assembly power distribution strongly influences both the location and magnitude of core-level power peaking.

To mitigate this, a reduction in the fuel assembly peak RPF by approximately 10%, comparable to the exceedance level observed in the optimal designs, should be pursued. Achieving this reduction would require new fuel assembly burnable absorber loading configurations. One potential solution is to combine the two absorbers used in this study within the same fuel assembly, leveraging gadolinia to effectively control BOC reactivity while using IFBA to flatten the power distribution.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This study evaluated the feasibility of an EPU in the STP Unit 1 pressurized water reactor through advanced core design optimization using LEU+ fuel and enhanced burnable absorber configurations. Leveraging a POLARIS then PARCS modeling approach with the MIDAS optimization framework, this investigation explored extended-uprated operating conditions targeting a 4500 MWth core and 700 EFPD cycle length. Initial optimization with IFBA-only LEU+ assemblies achieved all core-level performance goals except for excessive reactivity, leading to a high soluble boron concentration. Subsequent implementation of uranium-gadolinia fuel assemblies improved reactivity control and power flattening, but no core design simultaneously satisfied all performance and updated safety constraints under the original EPU objectives.

To establish more practical pathways for uprated operation, two reduced objectives, HPU and LPU, were developed. These scenarios relaxed either the cycle length or uprate magnitude while maintain-

ing thermohydraulic consistency. Optimization results demonstrated that both scenarios could achieve near compliance with all design limits, with HPU cases showing improved burnup performance and LPU cases offering more balanced reactivity control. However, both configurations consistently exhibited rod enthalpy rise factor ($F_{\Delta H}$) exceedance of approximately 9–12%, primarily originating from intra-assembly rod power peaking in fresh, high-reactivity fuel regions early in the cycle.

These findings highlight that power uprate feasibility in existing PWRs is strongly governed by fuel assembly loading design, rather than solely by enrichment or core-level shuffling strategy. To enable safe and economically viable uprates beyond current operating limits, future work should focus on developing new burnable absorber configurations that integrate multiple absorber types within a single fuel assembly to better manage both BOC reactivity and localized power peaking. Incorporating such hybrid IFBA–gadolinia designs, along with refined optimization objectives accounting for rod-level peaking behavior, is expected to enable safe, uprated LWR cores using LEU+ fuels.

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REFERENCES

- [1] The White House. “Safely and Responsibly Expanding U.S. Nuclear Energy: Deployment Targets and a Framework for Action.” The White House, Washington, D.C., United States (2024).
- [2] U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission. “Power Uprates – Types of Power Uprates.” (2025). URL <https://www.nrc.gov/reactors/operating/licensing/power-uprates/type-power>.
- [3] T. Downar, Y. Xu, and V. Seker. *PARCS v3.0 U.S. NRC Core Neutronics Simulator User Manual (UM-NERS-09-0001)*. University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI, United States (2010).
- [4] M. A. Jessee, W. A. Wieselquist, T. M. Evans, S. P. Hamilton, J. J. Jarrell, K. S. Kim, J. P. Lefebvre, A. B. Thompson, and M. L. Williams. “POLARIS: A New Two-Dimensional Lattice Physics Analysis Capability for the SCALE Code System.” In *Proceedings of PHYSOR 2014 – The Role of Reactor Physics toward a Sustainable Future*, Kyoto, Japan (2014).
- [5] STP Nuclear Operating Company. *South Texas Project Units 1 and 2 – Updated Final Safety Analysis Report (Rev. 18), Chapter 4: Reactor*. STP Nuclear Operating Company, Bay City, TX, United States (2016).
- [6] N. Rollins. *Development of an Advanced Framework for PWR Power Uprates and Equilibrium Cycle Optimization*. Ph.D. Dissertation, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, NC, United States (2025).
- [7] U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission. “Accident Tolerant Fuel – Burnup Extension and Fuel Performance.” (2025). URL <https://www.nrc.gov/reactors/power/atf/technologies/burnup>.
- [8] C. Sanders, J. Wagner, and R. Lee. “Study of the Effect of Integral Burnable Absorbers for PWR Burnup Credit.” Technical Report NUREG/CR-6760, ORNL/TM-2000-321, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, TN, United States (2002).
- [9] D. Driscoll, J. Downar, and J. Pilat. *The Linear Reactivity Model for Nuclear Fuel Management*. American Nuclear Society, La Grange Park, IL, United States (1991).